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The effect of teacher competence and motivation on performance through work satisfaction of teachers at Junior High School 7 Jakarta

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of competence and motivation on job satisfaction, analyze the impact of competence and motivation on performance, analyze the effect of job satisfaction on performance, analyze the impact of competency on performance through job satisfaction and analyze the impact of motivation on performance through job satisfaction on teachers in State Junior High Schools 7 Jakarta. In research using a research design, the causality research design between variables and the research method also illustrates the relationship or influence between variables. Data collection techniques use two types of data collection, namely secondary data and primary data. The analysis technique used in this study uses Path Analysis. The results showed that the influence of competence and motivation on performance through satisfaction could not be intervening variables. The calculation results obtained indicate that each exogenous variable's direct effect is greater than the indirect effect on performance. These results suggest that satisfaction cannot play an intervening variable between competence and motivation on teachers' performance at Junior High School 7 Jakarta.

Keywords: Competence; Motivation; Job Satisfaction and Performance

1. Introduction

National education efforts that are carried out to create quality humans require well-planned efforts and require advanced thinking. The implementation of the desired education is to create quality humans in the real sense of achieving success. As humans, beings who have a noble position compared to other creatures, of course, need special attention and extraordinary effort as a vehicle that has a particular brand has special care and maintenance instructions so that it does not suffer unwanted damage. Likewise, the condition of humans who have a purpose in life and a purpose in life requires a guide that must be implemented to maintain and achieve a life that achieves success, to achieve success in achieving this life goal, education has a huge role; even humans' success to achieve success in achieving their life goals will be determined by the education they receive.

Education is an investment in the future. One of the developed countries can be seen from the quality of education. The country's development will be successful if the education in the country is good. The role of education, in this case, is to form quality Human Resources (HR) that can keep up with developments in science and technology. Education is one of the areas that must receive significant attention.

One component in educational institutions that supports improving the quality of education is the teacher. The role of teachers in education is enormous, namely transferring knowledge to students. The teacher also educates, sets an example, and guides students to become human beings who are good at science and technology and have good character and personality.

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One of the educational institutions in Jakarta is Junior High School 7 Jakarta. Junior High School 7 Jakarta was established on January 22, 1951, and the operational permit SK number 246 / SK / B.II. Central Government Ownership Status. Address Jl. North Utan Kayu People's Hall. North Utan Kayu Village. Matraman District. East Jakarta Postal Code 13120 with a land area of 5654 M². This school is in great demand by students because of the school's position, which is quite affordable by facilities from the upper-middle to the lower middle class following the ability of students' grades that meet the specified requirements.

A formal organization is an organization formed or established in the presence of laws and regulations that become a legal basis. Human resources have an essential role both individually and in groups because human resources are one of the main drivers of the smooth running of business activities. Therefore, an organization needs to pay attention to and regulate its employees' existence to improve good performance. One example of a formal organization is a school. School is an educational institution that plays an important role in building individual morale from an early age apart from the most important factor, namely family. Schools teach a variety of knowledge that is not obtained from the family to broaden their students' knowledge. A successful school has good performance and can achieve its goals.

Teacher performance is the teacher's ability to complete duties and responsibilities as an educator, shown by optimal work results following educational goals. Teacher performance appraisal is indispensable as a teacher monitoring tool at work. This assessment is used as a material for evaluating educational institutions to improve teacher performance. Teachers who have optimal performance can be seen from teachers' ability to complete learning design assignments following school demands, carry out effective learning, and conduct learning assessments that can measure students' abilities.

The meaning of performance comes from the words job performance and is also called actual performance or work performance or actual achievement that has been achieved by an employee. There are three performance dimensions: task performance, contextual performance, and counter-productive performance [1]. [2] defines performance as the quality and quantity of work achieved by a person carrying out his duties following the responsibilities given to him. Performance describes what employees do, how employees do their jobs, and the results achieved afterward. The better the teacher's performance, the easier it will be for the school to achieve its goals and vice versa; if the teacher's performance is low, the more difficult it will be for the school to achieve its goals. The important role of human resources is that schools must use their human resources effectively and efficiently as possible to have good performance. An organization needs to pay attention to various factors that can affect employee performance because it requires an organizational role in increasing competence and job satisfaction. Because employees feel uncomfortable and underappreciated at work, employees cannot develop all their potential, and automatically, employees cannot fully concentrate and focus on their work.

One of the factors that affect teacher performance is competence. Schools must also pay attention to maintaining and managing employee abilities at work so that they focus on school goals. Maintaining abilities or competencies is important because teachers' competence is one of the keys to determining school success. Schools' success in educating their students is inseparable from the resources the school has, especially teachers. It can also be determined by the teachers' competence and performance in each school.

Competence is an important thing for every teacher because it can be a basic foundation that becomes a measuring tool for how an individual can see his or her ability to carry out their duties. [3] defines competence as a combination of knowledge and skills needed to carry out a task successfully. Achievement is evidenced by the individual's ability to collect data, rate processes into useful information, reach the right decisions, and initiate the necessary actions to acceptably complete the task.

Based on the factors that affect the aspects of teacher performance that have been described above, one that affects teacher performance is the work motivation factor possessed by each individual. This is reinforced by the opinion of [4] "... a person's work performance in an organization is very dependent on his motivation". Motivation is the primary drive that moves a person to behave. "This impulse is in someone who moves him to do something following the drive in him" [5].

This aspect of performance is related to the motivation that a person has. As stated by Uno and [5] "performance is the interaction between one's abilities and motivation." According to this opinion, performance is the sum of one's work abilities and motivation. [6] argues individuals who are not motivated will only give a minimum effort in their work. This shows that motivation is an important component in individual work performance. The conclusion, according to [6] is that motivation is related to a person's behavior and performance.

According to [7] "motivation cannot be observed directly, but can be interpreted through behavior." This behavior can be in the form of actions taken to complete the task. Motivation is the driving factor that influences human behavior. Teachers who have high motivation in their work will certainly be motivated to do the best possible work effectively and efficiently so that the teachers' initial goals that have been planned can be implemented properly. Of course, this motivation has different levels for each individual. Some have high, low, and medium work motivation, all of which will affect the performance that will be generated.

[7] argues that "the tendency to succeed is determined by motivation, opportunity and intensive, and vice versa by the tendency to fail." Starting from this view, motivation has an essential role in carrying out various jobs carried out by the teacher to achieve the goals that have been set optimally.

An individual who is competent to successfully carry out a task is proven by obtaining an achievement or achievement to cause his satisfaction. This is because he feels capable of carrying out his duties and responsibilities. Job satisfaction is an individual. Each individual has a different level of satisfaction according to the value system that applies to him. The higher the assessment of the perceived activity following the individual's wishes, the higher the satisfaction with the activity.

Job satisfaction is a combination of psychological, physiological, and environmental conditions that cause a person, to be honest, satisfied with his job ([8]. Lease in [8] states that employees who have higher job satisfaction are usually more likely not to leave work are more productive, display more organizational commitment, and are more likely to be satisfied with their lives. Job satisfaction is defined as a pleasure or positive emotional state resulting from job appraisal and work experience as a function of the perceived relationship between what is desired from a job and what is felt [9]. According to [8] job satisfaction is a feeling that workers have about their job or general attitudes toward work.

[10] says that employees who get job satisfaction usually perform better than employees who do not get job satisfaction. Employees will feel satisfied with the work that has been carried out if what is done is deemed to have met their expectations, following the work objectives. If a teacher has less competence, he will be motivated to take action to achieve these expectations. If his expectations are met, he will feel satisfied. Conditions in which employees get high job satisfaction are expected to have high performance as well.

Job satisfaction can be one of the variables that mediate the effect of competence on performance. Mediating variables are often called intervening variables or process variables. Mediation occurs when the independent variable affects the dependent variable indirectly through at least one mediator variable. If it only consists of one mediator, it is called simple mediation, and if the mediation process involves more than one mediator, it is called multiple mediations [11].

2. Literature Review

2.1. Competence

Competence can be defined as many things ranging from the things that the organization does well to the qualities that each employee must have, the knowledge and skills needed to perform tasks, and characteristics and attributes [3]. According to [3] competence has an important problem because competence is related to individuals and not jobs. As jobs change more rapidly, competencies are more useful because they are more effective than job descriptions at clarifying what characteristics are helpful. Competence can be used for self-defense so as not to lose to compete in increasingly fierce global competition.

Competence is a set of knowledge, skills, and behaviors that must be possessed, internalized. Teachers and education personnel must master it in carrying out professional duties at the Ministry of National Education [13]. According to [12], competence is competence, skill, authority, or fulfilling the requirements according to legal provisions. Competence as knowledge, skills, and basic values that are reflected in the habit of thinking and acting to [13].

So competence is a set of intelligent actions full of responsibility that a person must have as a condition to carry out tasks in certain fields of work. Intelligence must be demonstrated as skill, determination, and success in acting. The nature of responsibility must be shown as the truth of action from scientific, technological, and ethical perspectives. So teacher competence is the ability of a teacher to carry out his obligations responsibly and properly.

2.2. Motivation

Etymologically, the term motivation comes from the Latin *movere*, which means to move [6]. Motivation means encouraging, directing, and perpetuating behavior. The term motivation comes from the word *motive*, which can be interpreted as the power of an individual, which causes the individual to act and act. [7] states, "motive is the driving force within people to carry out certain activities to achieve specific goals. So the motive is an internal condition in someone to achieve the desire. Thus motivation is the impetus within a person to try to make changes in behavior that better meet their needs.

[14] States that motivation is an internal process that activates and guides and maintains a person's behavior continuously. Meanwhile, according to [6] "... motivation is the result of processes that are internal or external which lead to enthusiasm and persistence to follow the direction of certain actions.

[7] Argues that: "A motive is a re-integration by a cue of a change in an effective situation," which means that the motive is an implication of the results of consideration that have been studied (re-integration) marked by a change in the situation is effective. The main source for the emergence of motives is the stimulus (stimulus) of the current situation with the condition to be expected so that the signs of change appear in the affective differences when the motive appears and when the desired achievement is made, meanwhile, according to [15] states that "motivation is a change in energy in a person's (personal) self which is based on the emergence of feelings and interactions to achieve goals." This means that this motivation arises because of a need that must be achieved by someone. Another opinion put forward by [16] is that motivation moves and chooses to take any action towards the goal to be achieved. Meanwhile, according to [7] what is meant by motivation is "internal and external encouragement in a person to make changes in behavior," which has the following indicators: (a) the desire and desire to carry out activities, (b) there is encouragement and the need to carry out activities, (c) the existence of hopes and aspirations, (d) motivation and self-respect, (e) a good environment, and (f) the existence of interesting activities.

[17] States that motivation is a description of the relationship between the expectations that a person or organization has with predetermined goals because everyone has a goal in their activities. The relationships between expectations and these goals are manifold and always increasing, both vertically and horizontally. The description of this relationship is undoubtedly influenced by many factors, both from within and from outside. This expectation can be achieved depending on how the individual's efforts are trying to achieve it. From the various opinions expressed, it can be concluded that motivation is the impetus to achieving goals that are following what is expected. Internal and external factors influence this urge. Internal and external factors will lead to enthusiastic attitudes, which in turn will encourage changes in behavior. This impulse leads to more behavioral changes to achieve the goals that someone hopes.

2.3. Motivation

Views about work and work are often associated with an activity in a profession that is owned by a person. Because a person who does a job regularly and has specific rules in that job, this job can be said to be a profession. [18] argue that a profession is a position or job that requires expertise from its members. That is, just no one can do this work. The teacher is a profession because the teaching profession, in essence, and nature, requires basic requirements, technical skills, and certain personality attitudes [18]. In principle, performance leads to an effort to achieve better work performance.

[5] Defines performance as an interaction between a person's abilities and motivation. Based on this opinion, it can be concluded that a teacher who has high work motivation will certainly create a good performance. Because a teacher who has high motivation will consider all the problems, he faces as a challenge. This challenge will encourage the completion of all the tasks to the fullest because motivation is an encouragement that the individual owns to do his job and possible. Teachers who have high motivation will always work hard to overcome all kinds of problems they face hoping that they will achieve better or optimal results.

[7] Defines that work motivation is one factor that determines a person's performance. Teacher work motivation is nothing but a process carried out to mobilize teachers so that their behavior can be directed at concrete efforts to achieve predetermined goals. Meanwhile, according to [19] work motivation creates enthusiasm or work motivation. These drives can be internal or external and can be strong and weak. So motivation is a model in mobilizing and directing teachers to carry out their duties in achieving the goals/objectives set with full awareness and full responsibility. In line with [19], according to [4] Motivation is a driving force that results in a member of the organization willing and willing to mobilize abilities - in the form of expertise or skills - energy and time to carry out various activities that are their responsibility and fulfill obligations, to achieve the goals and objectives of the organization that have been previously determined.

From this description and regarding the meaning of motivation, in this study, what is meant by teacher work motivation is the power that is within a teacher to carry out various activities to achieve certain predetermined goals. This strength can affect the morale of the teacher so that it can be weak or strong. This spirit determines the performance a teacher will produce. Factors that can affect morale can come from within or from outside a teacher.

2.4. Job Satisfaction

[20] Defines job satisfaction as an attitude individuals have about their work. It results from their perceptions of their work and the extent to which there is a match between individuals and organizations. [21] suggests that job satisfaction is the feeling of supporting or not supporting employees experienced at work. [22] define job satisfaction as to how employees feel themselves or their jobs. These experts have in common that job satisfaction reflects both personal feelings related to their work, both positive and negative feelings.

Based on the expert's opinion, job satisfaction can be interpreted as a feeling that supports or does not support employees related to their work or with their condition. Job dimensions, according to [8] include:

2.4.1. Compensation

Increased salary and performance are ranked number one for job elements, while motivation and compensation are ranked number one for job satisfaction.

2.4.2. Work environment

The work environment is very influential on employee job satisfaction because it supports someone to do a job. A good environment will provide a sense of comfort and safety to do their work effectively and efficiently.

2.4.3. Supervisor support

Supervisor support is one factor for employee retention. Supervisory support is defined as the degree to which leaders care about their employees' well-being and motivate their contributions. A leader providing support makes employees feel motivated, heard, and

2.4.4. Watched for job security.

Job security is a condition in which employees will remain or are less likely to become unemployed if they have a higher level of job security.

Job satisfaction is the key to job satisfaction related to personal feelings about their jobs and other things that affect job satisfaction. The higher the sense of satisfaction you have with your job, the better the performance will be.

2.5. Performance

Etymologically, the term performance is a translation of the word performance, which comes from the word to perform, which has the meaning of (a) achievement, (b) implementation, (c) achievement, and (d) performance or work performance [23]. According to [24], "performance is technical operational or work power; demonstrated achievement and something achieved." Performance is an action or behavior to achieve work performance. [25] states that what is meant by performance is an activity carried out to carry out and complete certain tasks with full responsibility following the expectations and goals that have been previously set.

[23] explains that what is meant by performance is a form of behavior of a person or organization with an achievement orientation. The form of behavior produced by someone in the organization is in the form of results that come out of a job contributing to the organization. The results of this work are also called the achievements made by someone in the organization. According to [26] states, "that success in doing a job is largely determined by performance." The result of this work is the success of an individual or organization in achieving the goals that have been set. According to [23] what is meant by performance is "the work of a person in a certain period which is compared with several possibilities, for example, target standards, targets, predetermined criteria."

[5] suggests "performance is an act, an achievement or what a person shows through real skills." Based on this view, performance is an expression of the individual's overall potential because if not, the potential that the individual has will not be optimal. Meanwhile, according to [27] "performance is the level of success of a person or group of people in carrying out their duties and responsibilities and the ability to achieve the goals and standards that have been set."

Another view put forward [5] performance is "a person's activity in carrying out the main tasks that are assigned to him." In this case, one's performance is related to routine tasks performed by someone. Meanwhile, according to [23] what is meant by performance is "The level of success of a person or group in carrying out tasks following their responsibilities and authorities based on performance standards that have been set for a certain period in the framework of achieving organizational goals."

From the various definitions put forward by experts, in principle, performance leads to an effort to achieve better work performance. So it can be said that performance is a person's success in carrying out a job. Likewise, with Lawler and Porter in [5] performance is a "successful role achievement" that a person gets from his actions. This definition explains that performance is the result of a person according to the size applicable to the job concerned.

From several explanations regarding the term performance, it can be concluded that performance is behavior in the form of work achieved by someone. This behavior manifests achieving the expectations that a person has for a certain period and following predetermined standards. These standards or requirements that must be achieved are indicators of success in performance. The achievement of a person's expectations is a performance success.

Teacher performance is the ability shown by the teacher in carrying out their duties or jobs [27]. According to the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 14 of 2005 article 1 paragraph 1 concerning Teachers and Lecturers: "teachers are professional educators with the main task of educating, teaching, guiding, directing, training, assessing and evaluating students in early childhood education, basic education, and education. Medium "

[25] explains that at the operational level, teachers are a determinant of the success of education through their performance at the institutional, instructional, and experiential levels. In line with Surya, the Ministry of Education and Culture in [25] emphasizes that: "teachers are human resources capable of utilizing other factors to create quality learning and become the main factor determining the quality of education." The teacher is an important aspect, and the quality of performance must be improved because teachers with high-quality performance will produce good student learning achievement.

[28] states that teacher performance is the teacher's level of success in completing their work. Teacher performance is shown by work results and shown by work behavior, starting from lesson planning, implementing classroom learning, and evaluating or assessing student learning outcomes. Meanwhile, according to [23] teacher performance can be interpreted as the level of success of teachers in carrying out educational tasks following their responsibilities and authorities based on performance standards that have been set for a certain period in the framework of achieving educational goals. This performance standard is contained in the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 14 of 2005 Article 8 concerning Teachers and Lecturers that teachers must have academic qualifications, competencies, teacher certificates, are physically and mentally healthy, and have the competence to realize the goals of national education.

Teacher performance can be interpreted as a condition that shows a teacher's ability to carry out his duties and describes the actions that the teacher displays during the learning process [25]. [29] explains that what is meant by teacher performance is a communication process that takes place continuously, which is carried out in partnership between teachers and students. Concerning the performance of primary school teachers, teacher performance can be reflected in their duties as teachers and as an administrator of their teaching activities. In other words, primary school teachers' performance can be seen in the activities of planning, implementing, and assessing the teaching and learning process whose intensity is based on the work ethic and professional discipline of teachers [5].

3. Research Methods

3.1. Population and Sample

According to [30], the population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects with certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to study and then draw conclusions. The population was all teachers of Junior High School 7 Jakarta, totaling 60 teachers. The definition of the sample, according to [31], is part of the number and characteristics of the population; the sample taken from that population must be truly representative. The sample size is the number of samples to be taken from a population. According to [32], if the population is less than 100 people, the total sample is taken as a whole, but if the population is more significant than 100 people, 10-15% or 20-25% of the population can be taken. Based on this research, because the total population is not greater than 100 respondents, the authors take 100% of teachers' total population at Junior High School 7 Jakarta, namely 60 respondents. Thus the use of the entire population without drawing the research sample as a unit of observation is called a census technique.

3.2. Method of Collecting Data

Data obtained through direct surveys on the object of research with the following data collection instruments:

- Interview, which is a data collection technique that is done by direct questioning with the respondent.
- Observation is a data collection technique using direct observation at Junior High School 7 Jakarta teachers to match the data obtained from questionnaires and interviews.
- A questionnaire is a data collection technique done by giving questionnaires to respondents.

This method is used to obtain primary data. A list of questions is based on dimensions or indicators of competency factors, motivation, job satisfaction, and employee performance factors. The questionnaire was given to the soldiers identified as a sample.

4. Research Design

Figure 1 The Path Analysis Model

The framework for the empirical causal relationship between competence and motivation on employee performance through job satisfaction can be made through the following structural equations:

Structural equation 1 : $X_3 = PX_{3X1} + PX_{3X2} + e_1$

Structural equation 2 : $Y_1 = PY_{1X1} + PY_{1X3} + PY_{1X2} + e_2$

5. Results and discussion

5.1. Calculation of the Path Coefficient on the Substructure 1

The causal relationship between variables in sub-structure 1, shown in Figure 8, consists of one endogenous variable, X3, and two exogenous variables, X1 and X2. The structural equation for sub-structural I is as follows: Structural equation 1: $X_3 = PX_{3X1} + PX_{3X2} + e_1$

The results of data processing using SPSS software are displayed in tables 4.11 to table 6, summarizing the results of calculations and testing the path coefficients in table 1. Overall test or F test on sub-structure I with probability sig = 0.000 or significant for $\alpha = 0.05$ can be continued with an individual test or t-test. A summary of the results of the t-test calculations is presented in the table below:

Table 1 Model 1: Anova X1 and X2 on Y1

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1031.564	2	515.782	37.878	.000b
	Residual	776.170	57	13.617		

Total	1807.733	59			
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a. Dependent Variable: Job_Satisfaction
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Motivation, Competence

Table 2 Model 1: Coefficients X1 and X2 on Y1

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.754	2.238		.337	.737
	Competence	.383	.071	.539	5.383	.000
	Motivation	.278	.086	.325	3.240	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Job_Satisfaction

Table 3 Model 1: Summary X1 and X2 on Y1

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate
1	.755a	.571	.556	3.690

a. Predictors: (Constant), Job_Satisfaction, Competence

Table 4 Summary of Calculation and Testing Results

Sub-Structure Path Coefficient 1

Line	Path Coefficient	Probability Sig	$\alpha = 0.05$	Information
PX3X1	0.539	0.000	0.05	Significant
PX3X2	0.325	0.002	0.05	Significant

The table above shows that all path coefficients are significant at $\alpha = 0.05$ because all probability sig is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. So the sub-structure model 1, namely the relationship between X1 and X2 to X3, does not need to be fixed with the trimming model.

Based on the analysis results in table 1, the path coefficient value of X1 to X3 is $PX3X1 = 0.539$, and X2 to X3 is $PX3X2 = 0.325$. In comparison, the determinant coefficient (R Square) or the contribution of X1 and X2 to X3 is 0.571 as in table 2, which means that 57.1% of the variation in Satisfaction (X3) can be explained by variations in Competence (X1) and Motivation (X2). While the residual coefficient $e1 = 0.429$ or 42.9% is the influence of other variables outside of X1 and X2. Thus the structural equation for Sub-Structure 1 is $Y1 = 0.539 X1 + 0.325 X2 + 0.429$. Where the path diagram can be presented in the following image:

Figure 2 Full Sub-Structure I with Coefficient Value

5.2. Calculation of the Path Coefficient on the Substructure 2

The causal relationship between sub-structure 2 consists of one endogenous variable, namely Y1, with three exogenous variables, namely X1, X2, and X3. The structural equation for sub-structural 2 is as follows: Structural equation 2: $Y1 = PY1X1 + PY1X3 + PY1X2 + e2$

Data processing results using SPSS software are shown in tables 4:15 to table 10 with a summary of the results of calculations and testing the path coefficients in table 10. Overall test or F test on sub-structure II with a probability sig = 0.000 or significant for $\alpha = 0.05$ can be continued with an individual test or t-test. A summary of the results of the t-test calculations is presented in table 5.

Table 5 Model 2: Anova X1, X2, and Y1 on Y2

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1988.767	3	662.922	22.374	.000b
	Residual	1659.233	56	29.629		
	Total	3648.000	59			

Table 6 Model 2: Coefficients X1, X2 and Y1 on Y2

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.721	3.304		.521	.605
	Competence	.440	.129	.436	3.411	.001
	Motivation	.504	.138	.414	3.662	.001
	Job_Satisfaction	.004	.195	.405	3.522	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Table 7 Model 2: Summary X1, X2, and Y1 on Y2

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate
1	.738a	.545	.521	5.443

Predictors: (Constant), Job_Satisfaction, Motivation, Competence

Sub-Structure Path Coefficient 2

Table 8 Summary of Calculation and Testing Results

Line	Path Coefficient	Probability Sig	$\alpha = 0.05$	Information
PY1X1	0.436	0.001	0.05	Significant
PY1X3	0.414	0.001	0.05	Significant
PY1X2	0.405	0.001	0.05	Significant

The table above shows that all path coefficients are significant at $\alpha = 0.05$ because all probability sig is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. So the sub-structure model 2, namely the relationship between X1, X2, and X3 against Y1, does not need to be fixed with the trimming model.

Based on the results of the analysis in the table above, it is obtained that the path coefficient value X1 to Y1 is PY1X1 = 0.436; Y1 against X3 is PY1X3 = 0.414; X2 to Y1 is PY1X2 = 0.405 while the determinant coefficient (R Square) or the contribution of X1, X2 and X3 to Y1 is 0.545 as in table 13 which means that 54.5% of Y1 variations can be explained by variations incompetence (X1), motivation (X2) and satisfaction (Y1). Meanwhile, the residual coefficient $e_2 = 0.535$ or 53.5% influences other variables outside X1, X2, and X3. Thus the structural equation for Sub-Structure 1 is $Y_1 = 0.436 X_1 + 0.405 Y_1 + 0.414 X_2 + 0.535$ where the path diagram can be presented in the following figure:

Figure 3 Full Sub-Structure II with Coefficient Value

6. Conclusion

Based on the research that has been done, several conclusions are obtained, namely as follows:

- Based on the calculations that have been done in the previous section, it can be concluded that statistically, competence and motivation have a significant effect on job satisfaction at Junior High School 7 Jakarta.
- From the results of the calculations that have been done, it can be seen that competence and motivation on performance have a significant effect. But not only that, I can say that these two scores are still low, but it is good that the principal should also think about increasing competence and motivation to improve the performance of teachers at Junior High School 7 Jakarta.
- Job satisfaction in performance can be said that job satisfaction has a significant impact on teacher performance. Still, the results' value can be noted that the teachers are satisfied with the work that the teacher is doing.
- If seen from the influence of competence on performance through satisfaction, satisfaction cannot be an intervening variable; this can be seen from the comparison between the direct effect and the indirect effect where the results are more significant than the direct impact of the indirect effect.
- If seen from the influence of motivation on performance through satisfaction, satisfaction cannot be an intervening variable; this can be seen from comparing the direct effect and the indirect effect. The results are more significant than the direct impact of the indirect effect.

Suggestions

Based on the above conclusions, the suggestions that can be recommended are as follows:

- Based on the analysis and discussion and conclusions above, that motivation increases teachers' satisfaction and performance at Junior High School 7 Jakarta. However, the school should take other steps in maintaining or improving motivation.
- Another factor, namely competence has been able to increase job satisfaction and teacher performance. However, it would be nice if the school itself still maintains and improves competence.
- For other researchers, who want to research similar topics, it is suggested to sharpen the research that has been done by linking the competency and motivation factors of teachers with the formation of work ethics. This is indicated because work ethic is related to good perceptions (responsible, resilient, and hardworking), while good perceptions arise because of various motives.

Compliance with ethical standards

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